

To:
Nature Positive Initiative
Via email: metrics@naturepositive.org

24 Mar 2026

Re: Additional Input in response to Final Consultation on NPI State of Nature Metrics

Dear Nature Positive Initiative Team,

Thank you very much for opening your proposal once more for public consultation.

I highly welcome the ambition of the Nature Positive Initiative (NPI) to foster consensus on a small set of metrics to evaluate changes in the state of nature.

The NPI recommendations will potentially be taken up by frameworks such as the Taskforce on Nature Related Financial Disclosures (TNFD), the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), the Science Based Target Network (SBTN), the European Union's Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD), and the Finance Corporation Performance Standard 6 (Biodiversity Conservation). Once adopted by these frameworks, the NPI architecture is likely to become subject to intense public scrutiny. Should this reveal major flaws and weaknesses, a public backlash against private-sector led initiatives to ensure biodiversity protection can be expected, undermining a tremendous opportunity to mobilize private resources in support of conservation and to achieve the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity through transformative change within the very fabric of modern industrial societies [1].

It is therefore important that we get this right.

This consultation input is specifically concerned with the metric for Species Extinction Risk. I am focusing on this metric because:

- Even by the lowest estimates, humanity is extinguishing approximately one species per day. The UN Convention on Biological Diversity has estimated the rate as 150 per day.¹ See [2] for a discussion of the uncertainty.

¹ <https://www.cbd.int/doc/speech/2007/sp-2007-05-22-es-en.pdf>

- Unlike recovery from habitat loss, recovery from species loss will take tens of millions of years [3]. By comparison, recovery from climate change, lasting tens of thousands of years, is fast [4, 5].
- Halting species extinctions is a classical common goods problem, similar to climate protection: our own contributions give us little in return. An agreed formal system to internalise externalities is therefore required.
- There are tremendous opportunities to reduce species extinction risk at low cost through targeted action and avoidance of harm.

Unfortunately,

1. NPI's new, "final" description of the Extinction Risk metric differs substantially from the last draft, published for consultation in October 2024².
2. NPI's new description of the Extinction Risk metric unnecessarily and substantially violates NPI's own design principles for the framework, undermining the framework's efficacy.
3. The violations are uniformly such that they favour the STAR_T methodology, in which organisations internally advising NPI have commercial interests [6].
4. The STAR_T methodology, in turn, is structured such that it minimises corporate accountability.
5. Consequently, the current architecture exhibits a structural bias that minimises site-level accountability, directly undermining the initiative's overarching mandate to drive genuinely nature-positive outcomes.

I shall in the following discuss specific issues.

Impacts on forests and trees are effectively excluded from the metric

The ecology

Across taxonomic groups, about 80% of terrestrial species globally live in forests [7, 8]. The most species-rich taxonomic group are arthropods (mostly insects and spiders). The best estimates of their numbers have been obtained by multiplying the number of known tropical tree species (most tree species are tropic) by an empirical factor of round about 130 [9], because many insect species are specialised to live on one or a few tree species. Trees also host a large diversity of other, more or less specialised, species, including birds, mammals, mosses, lichens, and fungi. A highly effective way, and perhaps the only way, to protect the bulk of global terrestrial species richness is therefore to protect the species richness of trees. Notably, the number of threatened tree species alone listed on the IUCN Red List is larger than that of threatened mammals, birds, reptiles and amphibians combined [10].

² <https://www.naturepositive.org/metrics/>

Figure 1: Species density (RSR) of trees in forests by country [11]

Now, tree species richness is, similar to the richness of other terrestrial taxa [12, 13], distributed extremely unevenly over global land masses. Figure 1 is a map of the estimated density of tree species, precisely, of Range Size Rarity (RSR),³ within forests by country (for numeric values, see Ref. [11]). Crucial is the logarithmic colour scale spanning a factor of over 10,000 in tree species density. **Species density in Madagascan forests (ca. 0.025 species per square km), for example, is over 100 times larger than that of forests in Paraguay (ca. 0.00023 species per square km).** Based on a simple mathematical model of species extinction risk, this factor 100 implies that clear-cutting 1ha of forest in Madagascar increases the global extinction risk⁴ of trees by an approximate factor 100 more than doing the same in Paraguay [14], and so that of all associated insects and other taxa. More generally, the global change in species extinction risk resulting from a local intervention is approximated given by the product of the affected area and the resulting change in local RSR [14].

The above example is pertinent because land-use change (of which deforestation is the primary component) is ranked as the number one direct driver of global biodiversity loss [15]. Conversely, reforestation of native forests is one of key measures to halt this loss and reduce the current high extinction risk. The impact of both drivers scales with the local species density (RSR). Deforestation is, in turn, to 90% driven by agricultural expansion [16], a process by which forest ecosystems are usually instantly removed rather than gradually degraded.

³ The metric Range Size Rarity (aka, range rarity, rarity-weighted richness, endemism, biodiversity significance) is widely used in conservation ecology. It is defined as the sum of the inverse range sizes of all species whose range covers a location. On spatial scales larger than the typical ranges of species it becomes identical to species density.

⁴ The number of extinctions expected in the long term.

What NPI should recommend

Considering the above, a metric capturing the bulk of global terrestrial change in species extinction risk due to commercial activity (including many actual but undocumented extinctions) is given as follows:

The product of deforested (negative impact) or afforested (positive impact) area with the value of local tree RSR in forests.

This is identical to the sum over all tree species of the proportion of the global area of habitat of the species that falls within the affected site, except that a consistent spatial scale is used to determine both the sizes of ranges and the sizes of changes (see below for why this is important).

The metric is easily computed. Due to the wide global variation in RSR values (Figure 1), country-level data will often be sufficient to inform management and investment decisions. If higher spatial resolution is required, one can resort to forest-dwelling taxa as proxies [17, 18]. More detailed maps of tree RSR are available as well⁵ [19] and even more detailed maps could now be derived from the recently completed Global Tree Assessment [10].

The RSR metric is well established in the literature. Conservation ecologists have used RSR for species conservation decisions since 1991 [20]. Change in local RSR due to deforestation has been used, for example, to identify areas of recent high forest biodiversity loss [17] and to establish that from 2001 to 2015 the increase in species extinction risk due to deforestation caused by 24 developed countries was 15 times larger outside their own borders than domestically [18] (revealing a high risk of leakage from domestic conservation policies in developed countries). Because the theory of how local RSR change approximates change in global extinction risk is well understood, edge cases where this simple approximation breaks down can be consistently handled [14].

The RSR metric empowers corporations and financial institutions to contribute substantially to a reduction in species extinction risk by steering negative impacts away from regions of high RSR, especially in forests.

What NPI recommends instead

NPI guidance does not require inclusion of tree species in extinction risk assessments.⁶

⁵ References [11] and [19] differ because [19] did not divide RSR by the proportion of forested land in each region.

⁶ The 2026 *Draft Measurement Guidance* for species extinction risk ([21], p. 21) mandates that the measurement must:

Sum the proportion of the global area of habitat of each species in scope that falls within the site.

However, the 2026 documentation avoids defining what constitutes a species being "in scope" for this specific metric (it clearly does not mean species whose habitat overlaps within the site). The *Draft Measurement Guidance* explicitly limits its new "Species Selection Filter" to the "species populations metric only" ([22], p. 12), leaving the baseline scope for Extinction Risk completely undefined. Without a biological definition, "in scope" functionally defaults to the technical limitations of the chosen data layer (e.g., STAR_T), allowing users to silently omit the entire plant kingdom in compliance with the guidelines.

Assessment of extinction risk according to NPI guidance might still cover forest dwelling vertebrates. The recommended gold standard (the “high granularity assessment”) is Calibrated STAR_T (NPI Draft Measurement Guidance Executive Summary: State Of Nature Metrics [22], p. 21). The IUCN document specifying this methodology [23] contains a series of worked examples narrating how to determine Calibrated STAR_T for a hypothetical company “planning to create plantations for agricultural products” in Madagascar. According to the methodology:

- Deforestation in Madagascar at the plantation sites or resulting from displacement of local production from the plantation sites (IUCN Threat Class “agro-industry farming” [24]) is not considered to contribute to species extinction risk.
- Instead, the most impactful Threat Class identified is shifting agriculture⁷ by local community members at a rate of “50 ha/year, equivalent to 1% of the site per year” ([23], p. 62).
- Determination of Calibrated STAR_T includes an assessment, in consultation with all stakeholders, of what a site’s important contributions to species extinction risk are—removal of which would eliminate the site’s adverse impact. In the worked example these are the shifting agriculture and, to a lesser extent, trapping of lemurs.
- **IUCN concludes that after full removal of these threats the newly created 5000 ha (= 50 km²) corporate agricultural site in Madagascar would not contribute to species extinction risk anymore.**

By comparison, the established methodology based on RSR change would assess that the site increases global species extinction risk by up to⁸ about $50 \text{ km}^2 \times 0.025 \text{ species/km}^2 = 1.25 \text{ species}$ of trees and so round about $130 \times 1.25 = 162$ species of insects (see [14] for how change in extinction risk is quantified in units of “species”). Impact on lemurs could be assessed along similar lines. Because shifting agriculture involves ecological recovery of used sites after a few years, assessed impact on species extinction risk would be small by comparison.

What are the practical implications?

By implicitly removing trees from the species mandated for inclusion in the extinction risk metric, NPI makes room for the use of STAR_T. The STAR_T methodology, in turn, minimises direct threats to species resulting from deforestation due to agricultural expansion, likely the strongest driver of species loss.

NPI violates NPI’s design principle not to single out a specific methodology

NPI emphasizes in its documentation ([25], p. 11) that:

⁷ A traditional farming system where a plot of land is cleared, cultivated for a few years, and then abandoned to allow natural recovery.

⁸ The estimate depends on where in Madagascar the site is located (trapping of lemurs and shifting agriculture suggests location in a forested area), whether the corporate plantation replaces existing agricultural activity, and if yes how the existing activity is displaced.

NPI does not specifically recommend named metrics (e.g., Simpson Diversity Index), but provides a description with key characteristics.

Yet, between the 2024 draft and the 2026 “final stage” draft the Measurement Specifications Guidance of the extinction risk metric was modified from a generic guidance covering a shortlist of proposed metrics implementations for species extinction risk [26] to “strongly” recommend characteristics singling out STAR_T (which weights species by IUCN threat status) and modifying it from the original definition [27] to rely on “a specified historical reference range” for each species.

Original 2024 guidance was ([28], p. 8):

Assessment to be based on the summed proportion of each species range [or area of habitat] present within the location, optionally compared to a reference level, and optionally weighted by threat status.

The latest Measurement Specifications Guidance reads ([21], p. 21):

Sum the proportion of the global area of habitat of each species in scope that falls within the site. It is strongly recommended to weight each species by threat status and/or use proportion of a specified historical reference range, except when robust assessments of extinction risk are unavailable at global, regional, or national levels.

No rationale is provided for these changes.

The trouble is that what NPI “strongly” recommends without providing a rationale causes tremendous problems down the line.

One of these problems is that the ambiguity of the metric becomes so large as to make it meaningless. For the original STAR_T metric, a local increase in its value can result from both, something nature-positive (a vulnerable or threatened species extended its range into the local area) or something nature-negative (the threat level of a local species has increased). Local change in the STAR_T metric is therefore uninterpretable. The metric was not designed to quantify local contributions to change in extinction risk [27]. A simple solution to this problem is to revert to the scientifically well-established RSR metric by omitting the weighting by threat level. Any existing STAR_T data layer is easily converted to an RSR layer by omitting the confounding weighting factors.

Instead, NPI attempts to overcome the ambiguity by recommending use of a fixed “specified historical reference range” for each species, following a corresponding provision in IUCN technical documentation [23]. The metric value can then change only through changes in IUCN-marketed species threat levels. Unclear is, however, how such a “historic reference range” could defensibly be determined. Species, especially rare ones, slowly but continuously change the sizes and locations of their ranges [29, 30], not only due to anthropogenic and natural environmental change but also as part of intrinsic ecosystem dynamics [31]. While it might occasionally be possible to reconstruct the range of a species at a specified historic reference date, this choice and its consequences would be entirely arbitrary, making organisations responsible for the fate of species over which they have no influence.

What are the practical implications?

At the risk of undermining the credibility of NPI, STAR_T received a ‘strong’ endorsement.

NPI violates its design criterion that metrics need to be responsive

From the start, NPI specified six “Metric design criteria” for its work ([21], p. 6). One of them is to be “Responsive”, specifically: “responsiveness to changes made by users” ([32], p. 2).

Consequently, the original Metric Descriptor contained this element or responsiveness ([28], p. 8):

Species extinction risk score and trend over previous years (+/-) showing the contributions of a site and its surrounding area to extinction risk of threatened species

While this element of responsiveness was retained for the high-level descriptors of the other three metrics now for consultation, it has disappeared from the extinction risk descriptor, which now reads ([21], p. 15):

Species extinction risk measurement showing the contributions of the site to global extinction risk

NPI argues that this became necessary because the “frequency of updates of datasets” was a key challenge or barrier to uptake of this metric during piloting ([21], p. 12). For the STAR_T metric, relying on IUCN threat levels, this is indeed a major issue, especially for the variant using rigidly defined historic ranges. IUCN’s official goal is to reassess the threat level of every species every 5 to 10 years [33], although it often takes longer. These time intervals are not unreasonable. The five IUCN threat levels are a rather coarse classification, macroecological processes can be slow, and so it easily takes ten years or longer for a species to move from one category to the next. Of course, this classification is generally not responsive to changes made by any particular user and therefore unsuitable for an attribution of impact.

However, for all the other shortlisted metric implementations for species extinction risk [26] this problem does not exist. The response of local RSR to deforestation, for example, is immediate and so easily attributable.

Apparently, concerns about the “frequency of updates of datasets” arose during piloting simply because STAR_T was the only extinction risk metric seriously tested in the process ([21], p. 12).

What are the practical implications?

Rather than making use of the piloting feedback and identifying lack of responsiveness as a weakness of STAR_T (or other metrics relying on IUCN threat-levels) in the NPI context, the extinction risk metric descriptor was adjusted in a way breaching NPI’s own, entirely reasonable design criterion to accommodate this issue.

Corporate accountability magically disappears

The ecology

Similar to objects with fractal geometry, the size of the range of a species depends on the spatial scale at which it is measured. A well-established law of spatial ecology is that the number of species found in an area of size A scales approximately as a power of area with some exponent z with a value in the range 0.2 to 0.5 [29]. The phenomenon can be reproduced in simulations [30, 34] and is theoretically well understood [35, 36, 37]. The law implies that, if one counts species within A in small sub-areas of size A' , only a proportion $(A'/A)^z$ of the species in A will be observed in each sub-area. On average, the range of a species is therefore by a factor $(A/A')^z$ smaller when measured using pixels of size A' than when using pixels of size A .

What NPI should recommend

In order to determine the proportion of a species' range that overlaps with the local area affected by a project in such a way that impacts on the species are apportioned consistently over space, it is therefore important to measure range-size at the same pixel-size resolution in numerator and denominator of this proportion. For affected areas that are small compared to the pixel size A used, a consistent metric is obtained by employing the simplifying assumption that each population is evenly spread out over each pixel A .

This approach is not only mathematically sound but also ecologically reasonable. As mentioned above, the ranges of species are not static, especially not on small spatial scales. In order to survive, rare species require unoccupied space of suitable habitat that they can occupy in the future before they disappear, due to intrinsic ecosystem dynamics, from the locations they currently occupy. Indeed, when observing the distributions of species over very long time scales the value of the exponent z declines [29], implying that in the long-term average species populations are more evenly spread out.

It is therefore entirely reasonable, and even advised, to use species range maps that are rather coarse in species extinction risk assessment. More important is to distinguish between RSR in different habitat types, as habitat type can impose hard limits to the range of a species. Since on very large spatial scales RSR reduces to species density, no matter how range is measured, fine distinctions made by NPI between the "range" and "area of habitat" of a species may be of little practical relevance.

What NPI recommends instead

The NPI recommended gold standard for quantification of extinction risk (the "high granularity assessment") is Calibrated STAR ([21], p. 21). According to IUCN documentation [23], a major difference between the STAR_T data layer and Calibrated STAR is that species that are not observed at the site in question (or in the site's Area of Influence) are removed from the score (unexpectedly observed species are added). In effect, the ranges of species in the numerator of the range-proportions entering Calibrated STAR are therefore determined at a pixel size not larger than the area of the site. The nominal resolution at which the range size in the denominator is measured is 1 km. However, the effective resolution may be much larger, since the STAR_T data layer has not been determined using pixel-by-pixel ground-truthing surveys but relies heavily on modelling and interpolation between point observations.

If this methodology were applied to many small project areas that in total overlap the entire range of a species, the added proportions would not add up to one. In fact, a much smaller sum can be expected.

This problem gets amplified when a STAR_T data layer based on historic ranges of species is used to determine range size in the denominators of the proportions and species drop out in the Calibrated STAR numerator because they are or have not actually been observed at the site.

What are the practical implications?

The Calibrated STAR methodology recommended by NPI (and similarly the alternative “ground truthing”) is biased towards removing an unknown, potentially large, fraction of actual accountability for species extinction risk from corporate assessments.

NPI violates its design principle to quantify state rather than pressures

The ecology

Conservation ecology distinguishes between, on one hand, the ‘state’ of a species’ population, which includes population size, distribution, age structure, etc., and, on the other hand, its ‘status’, which summarises information not only on state but also on past and expected future pressures, population trends, the assessor’s risk tolerance, etc. [38]. Quantitative assessments of extinction risk (i.e. extinction probability over a given time horizon) can be based on status [39] or on state alone (e.g., on the hypothetical assumption that all pressure would subside) [14]. The resulting two conceptions of ‘extinction risk’, however, are different.

What NPI should recommend

NPI does not explicitly state which of these two conceptions the extinction risk metric is meant to refer to. The stated rationale of NPI, however, strongly favors assessments based on state alone:

- NPI explains that “The Nature Positive goal is designed to drive society to deliver a measurable absolute improvement in the state of nature against a defined baseline [...]” ([21], p. 3). Reductions in pressures or in the rates of decline of populations, while clearly contributing to improvement of a species’ ‘status’, are insufficient on their own to deliver such absolute improvement. Actual improvements in state are required.
- NPI does not deny that measurement and management of pressures, e.g., using status assessments, is important. However, NPI argues that “Measuring the state of nature is vitally important because it tells us whether our pressure and response actions are having the desired effect, i.e. are our environmental strategies resulting in improved outcomes for nature [...]?” ([21], p. 7). This is the central reason for going beyond status assessments and asking about material improvements in state, even if these are harder to achieve.

This rationale does not deny the central importance of measuring and managing pressures in conservation ecology. It just delegates this aspect to different frameworks. NPI is concerned with the end-point: the resulting changes in state.

There are additional pragmatic reasons for state-based assessments of extinction risk, encapsulated in NPI’s metric design criteria: Responsive, Accessible & Affordable, Auditable ([21],

p. 6). Status assessments are inevitably more complex than state-based assessments. They often rely heavily on expert judgement [33, 40, 41] and yet generate only coarse classifications. While this is entirely adequate for the original purpose of status assessments, which is to raise awareness of the species most in need of conservation attention under prevailing circumstances [40], such assessments do not only lack responsiveness attributable to user action (see above). They are also vulnerable to conflicts of interests arising in the context of commercial applications and are difficult to audit independently, especially when the intended use involves close interactions between corporate users and expert conservation practitioners [23]. The complexity of status assessments also makes them costly [33], especially when intended uses involve repeated re-assessments [23]. Finally, not least due to the high efforts involved, status assessments tend to be regionally biased [42].

What NPI recommends instead

NPI 'strongly' recommends incorporating species' threat status in the extinction-risk metric ([21], p. 21) and singles out the materially pressure-based Calibrated STAR_T metric [23] in the Measurement Guidance ([22], p. 21). The possibility of quantifying change in state-based extinction risk through changes in local RSR [14, 17, 18, 43] is not even mentioned ([22], p. 21).

What are the practical implications?

At the risk of undermining foundational principles of NPI, status-based assessments of extinction risk are endorsed.

I hope that you will find this response useful.

Sincerely yours,

Axel Rossberg

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